

OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF NATURAL-BASED SOLUTIONS IN URBAN AREAS – FRENCH CASE STUDIES

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1 KEY WORDS

Natural, disaster, flood, risk, resilience, management, upscaling, mapping

2 ABSTRACT

Observing current situation in urban areas and in light of recent events in southeast France, 'tempête' Alex in Nice municipality, the function of existing green blue and grey infrastructure is tested. While disasters have more and more drivers that involve human actions the role of nature and use natural-based solutions bring a new dimension of managing disaster risk and contribute to better understanding. In this paper we are analyzing existing natural-based solutions (NBS) in two case study area in France: (i) Nice Eco-Vallée located in Mediterranean and (ii) Les Boucholeurs located in west Atlantic coast. The two coastal case studies are part of Horizon2020 project RECONNECT (<http://www.reconnect.eu>) where the focus is on hydro-meteorological risk reduction by demonstrating, referencing, up-scaling and exploiting large-scale NBS in rural and natural areas.

3 INTRODUCTION

Floods that happened in urban areas are characterized by increased frequency and they are no longer just natural phenomenon. It's one of the most frequent natural hazard [1] [2]. This hydrometeorological processes cause significant damages and create disruption of physical environment and urban communities. It is understood that floods can't be stopped, but the reduction of damages and vulnerability of risk prone communities can be done. [3] [4] [5]. The UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction created a report¹ that analyzed the natural disasters that hits more frequently from 1995 to 2015. According to the research the floods are the most frequent natural disasters with 3062 recorded events. This represents 43% of all other disasters.

A lot of available solutions are in front of planners, engineers and urbanists. Traditional protection strategies were upgraded with unstructural measures and there was a light on social component too when looking on urban system. Protection and later adaptation to increased hydrometeorological hazards is happening now. Here we are reworking flooding processes in urban areas that are now facing new challenge, how to combine them in order to achieve cost-effectiveness, sustainability and overall sufficiency. In the last decade were with new perspective, the perspective of natural-based solutions.

Natural-based solutions can address societal challenges from climate change and urbanization in a suitable way [6].

¹ https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/COP21_WeatherDisastersReport_2015_FINAL.pdf

One of the main purposes of NBS is to address challenges, such as mitigation climate change, water management, land use, and urban development (Bulkeley et al., 2017). Promoted through policy (EC) [8] and by practitioners (in particular the International Union for Nature Conservation, IUCN), NBS become a way for the sustainable use of nature in solving societal challenges [9].

The NBS concept of working with nature and addressing social and global challenges is transformed into several goals and included in several reports. One of the reports is Final Report of the Horizon 2020 Expert Group in ‘Nature-Based Solutions and Re-Naturing Cities’. The reports focuses on: (i) sustainable urbanisation, (ii) restoration of degraded ecosystems, (iii) adaptation and mitigation of climate change and (iv) risk management and resilience. The multifunctional concept of NBS is also seen through UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which was adopted by all United Nations Member States (UN, 2015) [10].

What NBS solve and what is their contribution to overall sustainability of urban systems? As one of the guiding questions in this paper the concept of NBS is therefore a frame for creating sustainable urban systems to hydrometeorological hazards with its opportunities and challenges.

4 CASE STUDY AREAS

Here, we are presenting the two examples of how NBS is implemented in urban systems in France. We are providing a broader overview of existing benefits and challenges. The first, a case study area Les Boucholeurs, located in west Atlantic coast of France highlights the preservation of natural habitat as a buffer for accepting high tide from the ocean and at the same time provides an economic value to the area. The second area, low river Var valley, located in the southeast of France, in the Médoc provides a good example of how new land development along with the focus on new technology and existing natural habitat are creating an NBS system that is at some point a unique concept of future development.

4.1 CASE STUDY LES BOUCHOLEURS

“Les Boucholeurs” is a district of Châtaillon-Plage located on the limit of Yves, two cities of the Charente-Maritime prefecture. This district counts approximately 600 houses and has an important activity in oyster and mussel farming. Les Boucholeurs extends in border of a vast bay with the houses on the sea front directly exposed to waves as well as setback constructions on the location of former leveed marshes. The significance of this area is the extreme event Xynthia and its effect on the local community.

Storm Xynthia, in February 2010, caused a lot of damages. In Les Boucholeurs, the urbanized zone has undergone both, on the north area of the commune, overtopping on the sea front (the strong exposure to waves caused two deaths) and, south, water entrances on a very large linear direction due to levees and dunes overflowing. The canal that crosses the urbanized area (the Punay port canal) contributed to store the water in the high stakes zone. The foreshore ramps were not equipped with locking devices and allowed the passage of large flows. The lighter marshes were severely damaged after being submerged. Also, the permeability of road and railway infrastructures allowed a part of the water to spread outside the most vulnerable areas. The period after the event brought serious consideration of decision making process on local level and put on the table nature consideration and how to use its potential in order to buffer the existing hydrometeorological risks.

The existing waterfront has been converted into paved promenade. The dense urbanization started on the former site of embankment system combined with marchland (existing system of retention areas). This area was in a way a natural buffer boundary with the Atlantic coast. Its primary function was to compensate swells from the north and storms coming from the west.

Existing flood protection structures in this area is a flood protection wall rebuilt after Xynthia event. The protection wall is located along the sand beach of this area and with existing dune system creates a flood protection system.

Les Boucholeurs

Combination of protection structures: dunes and protection wall

Protection wall and flood gate

Figure 1: Les Boucholeurs and protection structures

1.1.1 Hydro-meteorological hazard and problem description

The Atlantic coast is threatened by storm surges and potentially by the sea level rise. Those events could contribute to the failure mechanisms of the embankments and could generate some important water level on the rear part of this area, which is lower than the coast line itself.

This was the case on 27th-28th February 2010, when Xynthia Storm reaches the French Atlantic coast. The Charente-Maritime department was highly affected by this event which generated € 1,4 billions of damages and 53 fatalities in France (2 on the site “Les Boucholeurs”). At the beginning of the project, the protection plan is ongoing but not all the protection measures were achieved.

After this event, in the hurry, the place “Les Boucholeurs” was designed as one of the main “Black Area” where all the houses should be destroyed. This impacted local community a lot due to their farming activities and living places.

Figure 2: Prefectural map with included flood risk zoning

Further discussions as well as strong participation of local stakeholders changed the marking “Black Area” into “Orange or Yellow Area”. Currently the new strategy for this area is created. This relates to reconstruction on the embankment system, new flood gates and set of non structural measures that will contribute to risk awareness. After this event, a large plan of protection measures was launched with some structural works: creation of breakwater, reinforcement of dikes, etc.

This tourist area is at the same time a place with oyster farming. Land use in total is divided on following: agglomeration 42%, marsh and coastal dunes (11% and 28%) and limestone plains 13%². The natural environment is defined with two elements: green and blue network. Forests, meadows and lawns, rivers and wetlands, dunes and beaches thus constitute heart of biodiversity and / or biological corridors. These living environments are the support of the green and blue wefts.

Elements of the blue frame are represented by diverse streams, then from the streams to the river. This is defining a network of wetlands that is representing the key element of the blue frame. The biological diversity of rivers depends directly on the quantity and the physicochemical quality of water resources throughout the year and the state of aquatic habitats: for many aquatic species, especially large migratory fish (salmon, eels, trout, shad, lamprey, etc), the possibilities of displacements are conditions indispensable to their survival.

4.1.1 NBS

Following the storm Xynthia in 2010, the municipality of Châtelailon-Plage has set up, with the municipality of Yves, Aix and Fouras, a system to fight against different types of flood called PAPI (Program of Actions Of Flood Prevention).

The purpose of this system is to protect people, goods and activities against the risk of marine flooding. The various actions are carried out within PAPI. The three major themes are considered:

- Prevention and forecasting: Improving knowledge and awareness of risk, surveillance, flood and flood forecasting, crisis alert and management.
- Spatial planning: Taking risk into account in urban planning, actions to reduce the vulnerability of property and people.
- The works of protection: Managing flows of water (from the sea and marshes), creation of protective structures (e.g., breakwater, reensablement, enhancement and thickening of existing coastal structures). The structures are designed to withstand a more important event than Xynthia (Xynthia + 20cm).

The demonstration NBS activities include:

- Multi-purpose wetlands (oyster farming risk reduction)
- Engineering solutions (hybrid configuration)

² Chamber of Agriculture of Poitou-Charentes, Program IGCS (Inventory, Management, Soil Conservation), 2007

Figure 3: Case study area, Châtelailon-Plage (Les Boucholeurs), France (Source: Google map)

Creation of NBS in this small coastal community is a very good example of how people are organized on local level in order to protect their living space. Following the consequence of the Xynthia on 2010, the imperative was to create a protection system based on the existing structures, green areas and use of existing canals.

Before catastrophe event, the protection system was presented with protection wall and several wave breaches. After the event several aspects were taken into account:

- Reduction of harmful consequences of a marine submersion on the population, the goods, the economic activities, the environment and the heritage.
- Promotion a system of protection and defense against the sea while preserving socio-economic interests.
- Guarantee the realization of the projects thanks to the financial support of the state and local authorities.
- Bring all the local actors together when setting up and implementing the scheme.
- Develop awareness of risk at the municipal level, especially among citizens, elected representatives and professionals,
- Optimize and develop alert and crisis management tools,
- Master urban planning and adapt it to risk.

4.1.2 Determination of risk reduction target / primary benefit

Targeting risk reduction and on the local level the various actions are carried. Actions were divided into four major themes:

- Risk Prevention and Prediction: Improving Risk Awareness and Awareness, Monitoring, Flood and Flood Forecasting.
- Alert and crisis management: communal organization for safeguarding populations.
- Spatial planning: Considering risk in urban planning, actions to reduce the vulnerability of people and property.
- Protective works: the management of water flows (coming from the sea and marshes), the creation of protection works (breakwater, groynes, recovery, raising and thickening of existing littoral structures, etc).

The general criteria were to create more protective system for upcoming events taking into account the type of flooding in this area. In this sense, the focus is on the structural protection e.g. littoral protection from the water coming from the ocean.

At final, a set of measures is chosen to insure protection of the population and property. These measures were mixture of grey, green and blue infrastructure. The grey infrastructure is presented with protection wall along the coastline of the area. The blue infrastructure is revitalisation of the capacity of the canal Punay. The green infrastructure is using the potential of marches were in consideration is the fact that this area is protected and marked as NATURA2000 site.

4.1.3 Stakeholder involvement in the identification of all feasible NBS measure(s)

During the event 2010, the whole area was hit and other communities bordering the Les Boucholeurs had significant consequences and damages. In 2011, Mayors of the communities Châtelailon-Plage, Yves, Fouras-les-Bains and Ile d'Aix joined forces to create a public structure for the protection of persons and property against the risks of marine submersion: SILYCAF. This union carries an important project of protection and defence against the risk of marine submersion on the 4 communes.

In 2018, this union evolved into a mixed syndicate in which the Communities of Agglomeration of La Rochelle and Rochefort are represented to oversee the management of aquatic environments and the prevention of floods. It consists of about forty shares estimated at 42 million Euros, which will have to be completed by 2021.

As mentioned in the paragraph above the focus is on the coastal protection, having on mind the type of flooding that occurred in 2010. In this case this was a reinforced protection wall, creation of flood alert tools and use of existing green areas, marches that will accept water in cases when it is necessary.

The rationale in design of the NBS was to use existing structures, do reconstruction and increase capacity of the whole system to accept the strike of upcoming storm surges.

The whole process of construction and reconstruction is under the guidance of already mentioned syndicate SYLICAF.

4.1.4 Details on the chosen design for the selected NBS

Rehabilitation of the canal de Port Punay was done as the first phase of the protection work in the village of Boucholeurs. The work took place between October 2013 and April 2014. During rehabilitation the canal banks, both left and right, were reconstructed in the 550m length. Also, the rehabilitation of the lock house is done. The total cost for this phase was 800 000 €. The reconstruction of the canal was creation of concrete culvert in the 550m length. The cross section presented in the figure below show the level of rehabilitation.

Figure 4: Cross section of the reconstructed canal de Port Punay

Figure 5: Revitalisation of the Canal de Port Punay, Les Boucholeurs

Next segment in rehabilitation is protection of the north beach of Châtelailion-Plage. Work was done from spring 2014 to June 2015, where a breakwater was created north of the Châtelailion coastline, and a new beach was born.

The North breakwater is consisted of shaped stones weighing between 1 and 4 tons implanted on 200m long and 20m wide. It is sized to break the swell before it reaches the coast. On the North Beach, in total, more than 80 000 m³ of sand were brought, behind the breakwater. This project involved a Franco-Dutch company specialized in dredging. The sand was extracted off the island of Oléron 16km from our side, and then pushed back in a pipe laid on the foreshore. Then, a bulldozer was tasked to level the sand as and when. An operation lasted more than 40 days. This project was completed in June 2015 and allowed tourists to enjoy a new beach that has grown to 16 000 m². This protection work has become a real tourist asset for the resort. Amount of works and studies for this section of the protection is 2.4 Million Euros.

Figure 6: Breakwater structures located in the ocean close to the beach

The next section was protection works of Les Boucholeurs. The first protection works were carried out in the spring of 2011. This work was consisted of reinforcement of riprap along the beach, installation of removable cofferdams at each opening on the sea and raising of 50cm of the wall between the Place André Hesse and the recreational area in Yves.

In overall the development made under the PAPI (Programme D'actions de Prévention Contre les Inondations) had a role of marine submersions control device. Under this programme the work done between October 2015 and 2017 was consisted of:

Strengthening the existing breakwater and creating two new breakwaters

- The linearization of the coastline with the reinforcement of the existing dike and the creation of a bitter maintenance track over 1.6km long from the Boucholeurs port to the Oasis road
- The creation of a runway at the foot of the structure for its stabilization and the passage of shellfish convoys
- Improvement of the rainwater network for the watering of submersion volumes
- The creation of hydraulic cutting works in the marsh
- Rehabilitation of the Port-Punay Canal Outlet
- The installation of removable cofferdams
- The strengthening of the eastern bank of the Port-Punay canal 450m upstream from the Port-Punay road
- Cleansing ditches in connection with the Port-Punay canal
- The creation of anti-submersion walls.

Amount of protection works Boucholeurs is 11 Million Euros. Regarding detail cost benefit analysis there are no data available. However, work done in Les Boucholeurs up to now is crucial for the population and the action taken to increase protection of infrastructure, property and people are already beneficial. For example, after the reconstruction and additional protection of the North beach, the tourist activities become higher and this have the direct influence on economical benefit for the commune. The reconstruction process is not finished yet and no maintenance plan is active. Having on mind that people in this community are very involved for sure the maintenance will be one of the priorities. In order to perceive full effect of NBS there are indicators that has to be monitored. The main constrain is the fact that there should be several comparison over certain time, several years or maybe decades, in order to draw valid evaluation. Nevertheless up to this time a several indicators are chosen and they are monitored. The three groups of indicators are chosen for monitoring of NBS: water, nature and people indicators. The monitoring plan for Les Boucholeurs has 8 indicators all together, of which 2 in category Water, 4 in category Nature, and 2 in category People, as presented here below.

Table 1: Monitoring indicators for Les Boucholeurs

Category	Indicator
Water	Flood hazard, vulnerability
Nature	Increase in riparian habitat, increase in wetland habitat, increase in green areas, distribution of public green space
People	Reduced need for management and maintenance of infrastructure and change in land and/or property values

4.2 CASE STUDY ECO VALLEE NICE

The Var Éco-Vallée in the Lower Var river basin is a flagship project of the French Government and represents an innovative approach to manage and combine different environmental challenges, including the hydro-meteorological events in suburban and urban areas.

Low valley of the Var river is a good example of a long history of human interference in its morphological and sedimentation processes. Different measures in the valley and upstream of it have been implemented over the years. At the beginning, the focus was on the structural measures followed by hydraulic structures along the Var river.

The new project Eco-Vallee, focuses on new urban development of this area forcing both, grey green and blue infrastructures. The highlight is on:

- Green dikes, combining the increase in retention capacity with the enhancement of habitats.
- Installation of eco-district in the upstream part of the valley in the village called St Martin-du-Var

Figure 7: NBS site, Var low valley, Nice, France

The innovation potential of the Var natural-based solutions is in the existing condition and it is expressed in:

- Monitor the upstream measures to reduce floods (NBS hybrid) and explore their synergies with the measures to improve the ecological condition of the river.
- The eco-conscious approach applied on the new buildings. Here the concept is applied on bio-climatic office building with green-layered outer facade.

Figure 8: existing building in the NBS (DB5) representing the bio-climatic concept

- Application of HPC modeling within the previous projects. As a result we have a flood maps in high resolution.
- A progressive embankment system of the Var river. In XIX century the owners of the land, at that time the land was agricultural, were responsible for the protection of the river banks. The protection walls were building using stones (picture left). The stones were destroyed during the flood episodes. In the XX century the new system is invented and applied: the "sugars" (picture right) bricks on the concrete revetment. Today engineers are calling this system rip-rap.

Digue des Sardes (1844-1851)

Digue (1861-1974)

Figure 9: Progressive embankment of the Var NBS (DB5)

- Evaluate the benefits of those combined NBS

- AquaVar project - with the initial goal of to develop a modelling system to study the hydrology, river hydraulics and groundwater hydraulics in the lower Var river valley. Within this project the monitoring stations are set and will be used in RECONNECT project.

The Var is located in Alpine area (southeast of France) and its characterized as torrential river with steep slopes. The river Var has a total length of 114 km, with the Tinée, Estéron and Vésubie as its main tributaries cross five main sub-catchments (Tinée, Estéron, Vésubie, Upper Var, and Lower Var).

The river section concerned in this project is the Lower Var in total length of 22km approximately, which was previously running freely between the valley slopes. Those featured large, very mobile gravel bars composed of coarse bed material. From the early 19th century on until the 1960s the river was canalized over the entire length of the lower valley, reducing its width (cross section) from about 1000 m (in average between valley slopes) to a 300 m, and even 200 m in the last cross sections close to the sea. To compensate the lowering of the river bed as a result of the extraction of building materials, fixed weirs were constructed to bring the water table back to its original level.

The area is located in a center of polar and tropical air masses resulting in the alternation of a rainy season during the cold season and a dry season during hot weather. The average annual temperature of 15° and a mean annual rainfall of 826mm conceal an uneven distribution of temperature and precipitation during the seasonal cycle.

With existing NBS focus is on making space for water, so the most important parameters is precipitation during both periods: winter and summer. The maritime influence is an important regulator of heat in the Alpes-Maritimes, which contributes to a moderate climate of Nice. In addition, there is the alternation of night and day flows occurring in the valleys of the Var and Paillon from land to sea at night and the sea to land as a refreshing breeze during the day preventing the formation of mist in the valleys.

The average temperature is 8° for winter period, while recorded maximum rainfall is in November. This phenomenon is explained by the arrival of cold air from central Europe that reaches the warmer waters of the Mediterranean. This interaction of cold air in contact with a warm sea explains the genesis of depression in the Gulf of Genoa, which produces the dominant flow from east to reach the area of Nice.

During the summer its characteristic dry period from July to September where average temperature reaches 22°. This phase of the thermal evolution is linked to the Azures, which determines the fine weather on the Cote d'Azur and the rainfall deficit.

4.2.1 Hydro-meteorological hazard and problem description

The shape of the area is river valley, with flat flood plains. These characteristics are influential on the risks listed for demonstration site especially for:

- Floods: they arise from extreme weather conditions that affect the flow of rivers and may cause intense storm runoff,
- Landslides: storm runoff during heavy rainfall on steep slopes can cause landslides, falling rocks, etc.
- Flood 1994. and storm Alex 2020

As mentioned, the Var Éco-Vallée in the Lower Var river basin is a flagship project of the French Government and represents an innovative approach to manage and combine different environmental challenges, including the hydro-meteorological events in suburban and urban areas.

Low valley of the Var river is a good example of a long history of human interference in its morphological and sedimentation processes. Different measures in the valley and upstream of it have been implemented over the years. At the beginning the focus was on the structural measures followed by hydraulic structures along the Var river.

4.2.2 NBS

Creation of new urban zone in the west part of Nice resulted in creation of NBS system unique by its size and technological innovation. Located in the west part of Nice, the new zone was challenging in many aspects. One of the main goals in the project of national interest is to create an urban zone under the predefined strategic content. The area is created on three complementary axes: ecology, planning and

economy. A priority is given to natural based solutions focusing on the river Var with the main goal to return stable longitudinal profile and balance sediment transport regime. These two components were disrupted in the last century with application of different measures that had a negative long term effect of morphological status of the river Var.

At the same time, the new plan is to change land use of floodplains taking into account major challenges, with enhancing the value of the area and develop the balance between nature, agriculture and urban development. The first step in this process was to preserve existing natural resources: water, soil and biodiversity potential. Next, the consideration of the natural risks within existing prevention plans and programs. At the end, but not less important the focus is on territory innovation, with application of technologies of the future, particularly those linked to sustainable development, in order to diversify functions and develop jobs and at the same time create the affordable housing prices to meet needs of the developed city.

4.2.3 Determination of risk reduction target / primary benefit

The main measure regarding the risk reduction is on river Var and revitalisation of the river longitudinal profile and stabilisation of sediment transport. On the other side, the urban habitat in the new development area is adapted to existing and projected natural risks. We are here speaking about new buildings, with new materials (such as wood, solar panels, energy efficiency materials, etc) and new innovative infrastructure.

All feasible solutions that met river restoration criteria and provision of the acceptable natural risk are adopted and applied. With the reasons explained in the paragraph above the solutions considered for the river Var and for the urban development of the floodplains create a system of NBS unique by its functionality.

4.2.4 Stakeholder involvement in the identification of all feasible, and the final NBS measure(s)

The whole zone is acknowledged as a one big project with high national interest, a national urban planning operation with particular legal regime. This unique legal setting is organized as follows; the French state and not the municipality is issuing land permits and in some cases building permits. The new development zone, within the project is within the Prefect's decision and not the municipality. Within this setting the French state invested financially in this project along with regional, departmental and local community's contribution.

The urban demand was one of the key drivers in starting this big operation. Operation started in 2008 year starting the Operation of National Interest (Opération d'intérêt National, OIN) of the low valley of the river Var (Eco Vallée Nice Côte d'Azur). Alongside with the creation of the OIN the urban development agency is established. The main purpose of new agency is to carry out sustainable development project with defined parameter. This operation structure is under the supervision of the State where the State is represented by the board of directors, composed of the State representatives, Region, Department and local authorities and in our case Nice Sophia Antipolis University, Chamber of Commerce and Industry and a representative of Sophia Antipolis. The board of directors is headed by Christian ESTROSI and the board is a key stakeholder for this area. The main mission of this entity is to manage any actions that are promoting urban and economic development of the area. At the same time the focus is on the diversity of urban function, social interaction in the new habitat and environmental protection of the area taking into account environmental risks.

This structural organisation has its life cycle. In March 2012, the partnership protocol is created for the period from 2011 to 2026 and this year (2019) the protocol is extended by 2032.

The design option is focused on restoration of the low valley with the main goal to heal morphological status of the river taking into account longitudinal profile and sediment transport capacity. Regarding the floodplains, the design is focused on new living and business development area that take into account sustainable development, diversity of functions, transportation hub, new jobs and affordable housing prices.

The rationale in the NBS design focuses on bringing natural look to the river bed while abandoning the previous measures that were focused on creation of set of weirs with small hydropower plants. Original design was optimistic with beneficial contribution to local agricultural land owners, increased green areas and energy production.

³ Prefect - is the State's representative in a department or region.

This selection resulted in morphological imbalance. In the figure below the original idea that was adopted in the 60's is presented.

Figure 10: original design of the weirs with vegetation

This setting regarding the restoration was not very efficient and imbalance of the river morphology was evident. The flood event that occurred in November 1994 called for serious consideration of moving the weirs (. Operation of lowering the weirs started few years after the event with primary effect of bringing back the balance to the valley.

Figure 11: An example of the weir 4 after the event 1994.

As stated in the paragraph above, the main criteria was to preserve a natural status of the river, focus on sustainable development in floodplains, taking into account natural risks and creation of affordable house pricing.

This specific setting was created under the project of national interest with main financial contribution of State. As a main decision maker the Prefect is responsible for the urban plan approval, construction permits, etc.

The selected design focuses on removing engineering structures and preserving natural look of the river. Mentioned event in November 1994 triggered the process of rethinking about approach. Today, the river started to get natural look, seeking for balanced morphology and retrieving natural look.

Figure 12: Effects after removing the weirs

As presented in the Figure 12 after lowering the weirs the longitudinal profile is corrected. Operation started after the event and still is ongoing process. Actual situation is focused on restoration of the equilibrium slope, scarce vegetation, and braided river. In the figures below the

Figure 13: Work done on the weir 9 before and after the intervention

Figure 14: Effects on the weir 9 after 2 years form intervention

Based on the main strategy with highlighted economy, urban planning and ecology the second part of NBS system located on floodplain is created as a set of mixed functions and uses. Here we are speaking about existence of different activities, housing areas, recreational and sport areas, public facilities.

The first smart grid on the neighbourhood scale is located here. The thermal needs of the entire set of buildings are covered by a geothermal production network that distributes the whole district.

The technical installations offer solutions, smart grid ready. Finally, the pooling of needs and mixed use batch will promote the optimization of the powers to install.

The projected building plan of the district is given below. The focus is on energy efficiency buildings with different urban functions (public buildings, schools, residential, recreational facilities).

2018

2019-2020

2021-2022

2023-2024

2025-2026

2027-2028

> 2029

Figure 15: Planned urban development in the area for next years

Low Var valley plans to monitor 8 Indicators, of which 2 in category Water, 3 in category Nature, and 3 in category People, as presented here below in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 2: Monitoring indicators for low Var Valley

Category	Indicator
Water	Flood hazard, vulnerability.
Nature	Restricted range species, number and type of protective species, type, density of native species.
People	Increasinf recreational opportunities of NBS area, reduced/avoided damage cost from hydro-meteorological risk reduction, number of cultural events in NBS area.

A partnership protocol was signed on March 12, 2012 between Éco-Vallée's funding partners. It specifies the distribution of responsibilities and commitments, including financial. The financial protocol is important for the leverage it will enable to put in place. Indeed, by sharing the 64.5-million-euro financing between the signatory partners, the protocol allows the EPA to commit nearly 379 million Euros of expenses for the plain of Var, which will trigger in their turn almost 2 billion Euros of private investment.

The public consultations are in place along with the decision that is coming from board of directors. The creation of NBS is influencing reshape of existing urban setting and creation of new urban habitat with ecological footprint. Along with establishment of decision makers for the area a guide for the purchasing and procurement is created. Guide of the Public Establishment Ecovallée Plaine du Var (hereinafter EPA) aims to provide the thread of the purchase, from the assessment of needs to the notification of the contract and its execution. It helps to ensure the conformity of procedures with the rules of the public order, while ensuring the consistency of the practices of the purchase within the whole of the Establishment. In addition, it facilitates the efficiency of the purchase of the EPA and the proper use of public funds. This guide has been drawn up in accordance with the provisions of Ordinance No. 2015-899 of July 23, 2015 and Decree No. 2016-360 of March 25, 2016 relating to public procurement.

As written in the paragraphs above the NBS system consider river Var and urbanisation of left floodplain. The new energy efficiency and ecological district are in construction phase. These actions are part of national project that is forcing new, efficient buildings that are consuming less energies. For example the energy for the new district come from renewable sources in 80% and 20% of energy comes from nuclear power plants.

At the moment there is no maintenance plan regarding NBS but finalization of this project will bring new procedures and policies that support this NBS system taking the maximum benefits from its characteristics.

4.3 NBS challenges and opportunities

While case study areas Les Boucholeurs and low Var valley give two different NBS systems there are potential challenges that needs to be considered.

- Les Boucholeurs: Increase importance of existing NBS and the multi benefits. While the engineering approach in protection is still the mayor, the NBS application should be more promoted. The solutions where mixture of grey, blue and green infrastructure is providing protection, additional economic benefit and wellbeing is something that need s further promotion.
- Low var Valley - The main challenge is the length of the project itself. An NBS system is one part of this project of national interest. Although the project will end in 2032 the full potential will not be presented during the RECONNECT project.

The existing NBS systems provide at least more sustainable solutions in analyzed areas with consideration of water, nature and people and corresponding indicators. While these solutions separately aren't something new, when they are combined in NBS concept there is a possibility to analyse the whole system from different perspective. In this case the analysis, monitoring and evaluation are crucial for decision makers since it is possible to see the full effect of applied solutions. The dynamics of urban systems is real and nowadays fast, therefore a system solution that takes into account water, nature and people gives challenging view of how we are mitigating hydrometeorological risks or coping with existing challenges related to those risks.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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